

0 Modellus: the concept and uses

Write a mathematical model... and then visualise and explore it!

1

Modellus 4, A Visual Introduction for Teachers

Modellus - C:\Modellus4\examples\circle with trig function.modellus

Home Independent Variable Model Parameters Initial Conditions Table Graph **Objects** Notes

Particle Vector Pen Text Level Indicator Analog Variable Image Geometric Object Origin Measure Coordinates Measure Distance Copy Image Clipboard

Mathematical Model

```

angle = omega * t
x = R * cos( angle )
y = R * sin( angle )
R = 100
omega = 60

```

Write a model, using functions, differential equations or iterations...

Graph

Visualize one or more quantities on a graph and, or, on a table

Table

t	angle	x	y
10.00	600.00	-50.00	-86.60
10.10	606.00	-40.67	-91.35
10.20	612.00	-30.90	-95.11
10.30	618.00	-20.79	-97.81
10.40	624.00	-10.45	-99.45
10.50	630.00	-4.29E-14	-100.00
10.60	636.00	10.45	-99.45
10.70	642.00	20.79	-97.81
10.80	648.00	30.90	-95.11
10.90	654.00	40.67	-91.35
11.00	660.00	50.00	-86.60
11.10	666.00	58.78	-80.90
11.20	672.00	66.91	-74.31
11.30	678.00	74.31	-66.91
11.40	684.00	80.90	-58.78
11.50	690.00	86.60	-50.00
11.60	696.00	91.35	-40.67
11.70	702.00	95.11	-30.90
11.80	708.00	97.81	-20.79
11.90	714.00	99.45	-10.45
12.00	720.00	100.00	-4.90E-14
12.10	726.00	99.45	10.45
12.20	732.00	97.81	20.79
12.30	738.00	95.11	30.90
12.40	744.00	91.35	40.67
12.50	750.00	86.60	50.00
12.60	756.00	80.90	58.78
12.70	762.00	74.31	66.91
12.80	768.00	66.91	74.31
12.90	774.00	58.78	80.90
13.00	780.00	50.00	86.60

Make an animation using the model...

Notes

t = 13.00 Min: 0.00 Max: 30.00

1 A first look of the interface

Learn how things are labelled and what they do

The screenshot shows the Modellus software interface with the following components and labels:

- Ribbon:** A top toolbar with tabs for Home, Independent Variable, Model, Parameters, Initial Conditions, Table, Graph, Objects, and Notes. The Objects tab is active, showing tools like Particle, Vector, Pen, Text, Level Indicator, Analog, Variable, Image, Geometric Object, Origin, Measure Coordinates, Measure Distance, and Copy Image Clipboard.
- Model Window:** A large empty workspace for building the model.
- Graph Window:** A coordinate system with axes ranging from -80.00 to 80.00.
- Table Window:** A table with a header row containing 't' and a value of 0.00.
- Workspace:** The central area where the model is built.
- Control Panel:** Located at the bottom, it includes:
 - Start / Pause:** A green play button.
 - Step Backward / Step Forward:** Buttons for navigating through the model's steps.
 - Independent Variable:** A slider for adjusting the time variable.
 - Replay:** A circular arrow button to restart the simulation.
 - Reset:** A square button to reset the model.
 - Hide / Show Case Boxes:** A button to toggle the visibility of case boxes.
 - Minimize All Windows:** A button to minimize all open windows.
 - Hide / Show Ribbon:** A button to toggle the visibility of the ribbon.
- Notes Window:** A small window for taking notes.

2 See it in action: a simple example with functions (a model of projectile motion)

What you will get on this example that illustrates how to make a model of a projectile motion... (click on the image to see the movie)

3

2a See it in action: a simple example with functions (a model of projectile motion)

Write the model on the Mathematical Model Window...

The screenshot shows the 'Modellus - New Document' window. The 'Model' tab is active. The 'Mathematical Model' window contains the following equations:

$$x = 50 \times t$$
$$y = 50 \times t + \frac{1}{2} \times (-10) \times t^2$$

The 'Graph' window is empty.

Use either the * key or the SPACE BAR to get the multiplication sign

To make an exponent, either click on the exponent icon or press ^

Keys Backspace and Delete can be used to correct mistakes

Shortcuts for Copy, Cut, Paste and Undo are the usual ones (Ctrl C; Ctrl X; Ctrl V; Ctrl Z), on the Mathematical Model Window and on the Notes Window

2b See it in action: a simple example with functions (a model of projectile motion)

Create a particle to see the motion of the projectile...

The screenshot shows the Modellus software interface. At the top is a ribbon with tabs: Home, Independent Variable, Model, Parameters, Initial Conditions, Table, and Graph. Below the ribbon is a toolbar with icons for Particle, Vector, Pen, Text, Level Indicator, Analog, Variable, and Image. The main workspace is divided into two panels: 'Mathematical Model' and 'Graph'. The 'Mathematical Model' panel contains the following equations:

$$x = 50 \times t$$
$$y = 50 \times t + \frac{1}{2} \times (-10) \times t^2$$

The 'Graph' panel shows a coordinate system with a horizontal axis labeled with -80.00 and -40.00. A yellow callout box points to the 'Vector' icon in the ribbon and contains the text: "To create an object on the workspace, use the Right Button or Click on an object on the Ribbon". A context menu is open over the 'Vector' icon, listing the following options: Add Particle, Add Vector, Add Pen, Add Text, Add Level Indicator, Add Analog, and Add Variable.

2C See it in action: a simple example with functions (a model of projectile motion)

Once the particle is created, select its coordinates...

The screenshot shows the Modellus software interface. The title bar reads "Modellus - C:\Principia\A visual introduction ... Java\models\3 projectile.modellus". The interface has several tabs: Home, Independent Variable, Model, Parameters, Initial Conditions, Table, Graph, and Objects. The "Parameters" tab is active, showing a particle named "Particle2" with a "Dino" appearance and a "Blue" color. The "Coordinates" section has two dropdown menus: "Horizontal:" and "Vertical:". The "Horizontal:" dropdown is set to "x" and the "Vertical:" dropdown is set to "y". A mouse cursor is hovering over the "y" option in the "Vertical:" dropdown. Below the "Coordinates" section, there are input fields for "Scale, 1 unit" with values of "1.00" for both horizontal and vertical. To the right of the "Coordinates" section, there are several checkboxes: "Value" (checked), "Variable Name" (checked), "Trajectory" (checked), "Axes" (checked), "Projection Lines" (checked), "Name" (unchecked), "Leave a mark eve" (checked), "Case1" (selected), and "Auto-Scale" (unchecked). Below the "Parameters" tab, there is a "Mathematical Model" window showing the equations: $x = 50 \times t$ and $y = 50 \times t + \frac{1}{2} \times (-10) \times t^2$. A yellow callout box with a black border contains the text: "Click on the Particle to see its properties..." and "Use the Horizontal and Vertical variable boxes to select x and y as coordinates for the particle". Below the callout box, there is a small diagram of a particle with a red square and a blue circle, with the text $y_x = 0$ next to it.

2d See it in action: a simple example with functions (a model of projectile motion)

Run the model...

Run the Model...

The Run button is also the Pause button...

The current value of the independent variable is shown as a small ball alongside an horizontal line...

The current value of the independent variable is also shown as a number...

... as well as the Minimum and Maximum values.

2e See it in action: a simple example with functions (a model of projectile motion)

The Maximum value of the independent variable t is too big... but can be changed!

The Independent variable has the following default values:

Labeled as t
Minimum of 0
Maximum of 50
Step of 0.1

All of these values can be changed on the Independent Variable Ribbon

Define a domain $[0, 10]$ for t : Minimum value is 0, Maximum is 10 units

Don't forget to reset the Model, if necessary, using the Reset button

2f See it in action: a simple example with functions (a model of projectile motion)

Play it again...

Run the model again... to check if the domain is correct

With a domain $[0, 10]$ for t , the projectile fly until the same height of the launching point...

2g See it in action: a simple example with functions (a model of projectile motion)

Place a Pen on the Workspace to make a graph of the vertical coordinate y...

The screenshot shows the Modellus software interface. The top ribbon includes tabs for Home, Independent Variable, Model, Parameters, Initial Conditions, Table, Graph, and Object. The 'Table' tab is active, showing options for 'Write', 'Names', 'Points', 'Projection Lines', 'Values', 'Pen', 'Thickness', 'Axes', and 'Name'. The 'Pen' checkbox is checked. Below the ribbon, the 'Mathematical Model' window displays the equations: $x = 50 \times t$ and $y = 50 \times t + \frac{1}{2} \times (-10) \times t^2$. The workspace shows a graph of a parabolic trajectory. The horizontal axis is labeled 't' and the vertical axis is labeled 'y'. The origin is marked with a red square and labeled 'y = 0,00'. The end of the trajectory is marked with a red square and labeled 't = 10,00'. A yellow circle highlights the graph area, and a red box highlights the 't = 10,00' label.

To place a Pen, use the right button or click on the icon on the Workspace Ribbon

Select the properties for the Pen on the Ribbon

The Horizontal scale was changed to 1 unit = 10 pixels because the default value (1 unit = 1 pixel) was too small...

The Pen can draw points or lines, just select or unselect the Points check-box

2h See it in action: a simple example with functions (a model of projectile motion)

And the complete model is...

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Mathematical Model

$$x = 50 \times t$$

$$y = 50 \times t + \frac{1}{2} \times (-10) \times t^2$$

Table

t	y
6.90	106.95
7.00	105.00
7.10	102.95
7.20	100.80
7.30	98.55
7.40	96.20
7.50	93.75
7.60	91.20
7.70	88.55
7.80	85.80
7.90	82.95
8.00	80.00
8.10	76.95
8.20	73.80
8.30	70.55
8.40	67.20
8.50	63.75
8.60	60.20
8.70	56.55
8.80	52.80
8.90	48.95
9.00	45.00
9.10	40.95
9.20	36.80
9.30	32.55
9.40	28.20
9.50	23.75
9.60	19.20
9.70	14.55
9.80	9.80
9.90	4.95
10.00	0.00

The trajectory is parabolic, as well as the function y... but these are two completely different parabolas!

The values on the table can be scrolled and shown with the scroll bar...

The Graph Window is minimized, as well as the Notes Window

Minimized Windows can be shown with a double click or a click on their top-right icon

Timeline: t = 10.00, Min: 0.00, Max: 10.00

2i See it in action: a simple example with functions (a model of projectile motion)

And now a complete movie on how to make the model...

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Modellus - New Document

Home Independent Variable Model Parameters Initial Conditions Table Graph **Objects** Notes

Particle Vector Pen Text Level Indicator Analog Variable Image Geometric Object Origin Measure Coordinates Measure Distance Copy Image Clipboard

Animation Objects

Mathematical Model

$$x = 50 \times t$$

$$y = 50 \times t + \frac{1}{2} \times [-10] \times t^2$$

Table

t	y
7.80	398.80
7.90	396.80
8.00	408.80
8.10	406.80
8.20	418.80
8.30	416.80
8.40	428.80
8.50	426.80
8.60	438.80
8.70	436.80
8.80	448.80
8.90	446.80
9.00	458.80
9.10	456.80
9.20	468.80
9.30	466.80

Notes Graph

Min: 0.00 Max: 10.00 t = 9.30

3 A more complex example with functions (exploring parameters)

Particle launched vertically, with different accelerations: what you will get...

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Mathematical Model

$$y = \frac{1}{2} \times a \times t^2 + v_0 y + y_0$$
$$v_0 = 50$$
$$y_0 = 0$$

Graph

Table

t	y
15.00	187.50
15.10	184.98
15.20	182.40
15.30	179.77
15.40	177.10
15.50	174.38
15.60	171.60
15.70	168.77
15.80	165.90
15.90	162.98
16.00	160.00
16.10	156.98
16.20	153.90
16.30	150.77
16.40	147.60
16.50	144.38

3a A more complex example with functions (exploring parameters)

Create the mathematical model...

Modellus - C:\Principia\A visual introduction ... Java\4\modelo exemplo.n

Home Independent Variable Model Parameters Initial Conditions

Particle1

Horizontal: 30.00 Vertical: y

Coordinates: 30.00 y

Colour: Blue

Scale, 1unit = 1.00 1.00

Appearance

Mathematical Model

$$y = \frac{1}{2} \times a_y \times t^2 + v_{0y} \times t + y_0$$
$$v_{0y} = 50$$
$$y_0 = 0$$

Write the Mathematical Model...

The independent variable is the time t ...

This model is a function y that represents the vertical coordinate of a particle launched vertically with a certain initial velocity v_{0y}

Initial velocity and initial coordinate are given on the Mathematical Model Window

a_y is a free parameter...

3b A more complex example with functions (exploring parameters)

Give different values for the free parameter...

The screenshot shows the Modellus software interface. The title bar reads "Modellus - C:\Principia\A visual introduction ... Java\4\modelo exemplo.". The ribbon at the top has tabs for "Home", "Independent Variable", "Model", "Parameters", and "Initial Conditions". The "Parameters" tab is active, showing a table of parameters:

Parameter	Value
a_y	-5.00
	-10.00
	-15.00
	0.00
	0.00
	0.00

Below the ribbon, the "Mathematical Model" section displays the following equations:

$$y = \frac{1}{2} \times a_y \times t^2 + v_{0y} \times t + y_0$$
$$v_{0y} = 50$$
$$y_0 = 0$$

a_y is a free parameter...

On the Parameters Ribbon, give three different values for the free parameter...

3C A more complex example with functions (exploring parameters)

Create three particles and attribute properties for the first particle...

introduction ... Java\4\modelo exemplo.modellus

Model	Parameters	Initial Conditions	Table	Graph	Objects
	Horizontal: 30.00	Vertical: y	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Value	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Axes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Leave a mark e
			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Variable Name	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Projection Lines	<input type="checkbox"/> Case1
	le, 1unit = 1.00	1.00	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Trajectory	<input type="checkbox"/> Name	<input type="checkbox"/> Auto-Scale

Properties for the FIRST particle...
Vertical coordinate is y...
Case is Case 1...

3d A more complex example with functions (exploring parameters)

Attribute properties for the second particle...

introduction ... Java\4\modelo exemplo.modellus

Model	Parameters	Initial Conditions	Table	Graph	Objects
	Horizontal: 30.00	Vertical: y	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Value	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Axes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Leave a mark e
	Unit: 1.00	1.00	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Variable Name	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Projection Lines	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Case2
			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Trajectory	<input type="checkbox"/> Name	<input type="checkbox"/> Auto-Scale

Graph

600.00

-1.20E3

-1.80E3

Properties for the SECOND particle...
Vertical coordinate is y...
Case is Case 2...

3e A more complex example with functions (exploring parameters)

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Attribute properties for the third particle...

introduction ... Java\4\modelo exemplo.modellus

Model Parameters Initial Conditions Table Graph Objects

Coordinates: Horizontal: 30.00 Vertical: y

Value, unit = 1.00 1.00

Value Axes Leave a mark e

Variable Name Projection Lines Case3

Trajectory Name Auto-Scale

Values

Graph

600.00

-1.20E3

-1.80E3

Properties for the THIRD particle...

Vertical coordinate is y...

Case is Case 3...

3f A more complex example with functions (exploring parameters)

Select what to display on the graph window...

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The screenshot shows the Modellus software interface. The top menu bar includes Home, Independent Variable, Model, Parameters, Initial Conditions, Table, Graph, Objects, and Notes. The Graph window is active, showing a grid with three curves: a black curve, a green curve, and a blue curve. The horizontal axis is labeled 't' and the vertical axis is labeled 'y'. The Graph window also shows options for Projection Lines, Points, Auto-Scale, Tangent Lines, Equal Scales, and Thickness. The Mathematical Model window displays the equation $y = \frac{1}{2} \times ay \times t^2 + v0y \times t + y0$ and the initial conditions $v0y = 50$ and $y0 = 0$. A yellow text box is overlaid on the graph window, providing instructions on how to configure the graph.

Click on the Graph Window...

Select y for the vertical axis in the first three boxes...

Select Case 1 for the FIRST value of y

Select Case 2 for the SECOND value of y

Select Case 3 for the THIRD value of y

The graph shows three curves representing different cases. The black curve is the highest, the green curve is in the middle, and the blue curve is the lowest. A data point is highlighted on the blue curve at $t = 3.97$ and $y = -354.04$. The horizontal axis has markers at $t = 0.00$, $t = 12.00$, and $t = 19.80$. The vertical axis has markers at $y = 600.00$, $y = -600.00$, $y = -970.20$, $y = -1.20E3$, and $y = -1.80E3$.

3g A more complex example with functions (exploring parameters)

Change the upper limit for the independent variable...

The screenshot shows the Modellus software interface. The title bar reads "Modellus - C:\Principia\A visual introduction ... Java\4\modelo exemplo". The ribbon menu includes "Home", "Independent Variable", "Model", "Parameters", and "Initial Conditions". The "Independent Variable" ribbon is active, showing the following settings:

- Independent Variable:
- Step (Δt):
- Min: Max:

Below the ribbon is the "Mathematical Model" section, which contains the following equations:

$$y = \frac{1}{2} \times ay \times t^2 + v0y \times t + y0$$
$$v0y = 50$$
$$y0 = 0$$

Click on the Independent Variable Ribbon...

Change the Max value for t : 20 units is a good value...

3h A more complex example with functions (exploring parameters)

See it all, as an image...

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The screenshot displays the Modellus software interface. The main window is titled "Modellus - C:\Principia\A visual introduction ... Java\4\modelo exemplo.modellus". The interface includes a menu bar with options: Home, Independent Variable, Model, Parameters, Initial Conditions, Table, Graph, Objects, and Notes. Below the menu is a toolbar with various tools: Particle, Vector, Pen, Text, Level Indicator, Analog, Variable, Image, Geometric Object, Origin, Measure Coordinates, Measure Distance, and Copy Image Clipboard. The main workspace is divided into three panels: "Mathematical Model", "Graph", and "Table".

Mathematical Model

$$y = \frac{1}{2} \times ay \times t^2 + v0y \times t + y0$$

$v0y = 50$
 $y0 = 0$

Graph

The graph shows a plot of y versus t. The x-axis (t) ranges from 0 to 24, and the y-axis (y) ranges from -1.80E3 to 600.00. Three curves are shown: a black curve (y = 9.90), a green curve (y = -970.20), and a blue curve (y = -1.95E3). The black curve is a parabola opening downwards, starting at (0, 0) and ending at (19.80, 0). The green and blue curves are straight lines starting from the origin and extending downwards.

Table

t	y
18.40	73.60
18.50	69.38
18.60	65.10
18.70	60.77
18.80	56.40
18.90	51.97
19.00	47.50
19.10	42.98
19.20	38.40
19.30	33.77
19.40	29.10
19.50	24.38
19.60	19.60
19.70	14.77
19.80	9.90
19.90	4.97

The bottom of the interface features a "Notes" field and a control bar with a play button, a slider, and a time display showing "t = 19.80" with "Min: 0.00 Max: 20.00".

3g A more complex example with functions (exploring parameters)

See it all, as a movie...

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Mathematical Model

$$y = \frac{1}{2} \times ay \times t^2 + v0y \times t + y0$$

$v0y = 50$
 $y0 = 0$

Graph

Table

t	y
19.10	42.98
19.20	38.40
19.30	33.77
19.40	29.10
19.50	24.38
19.60	19.60
19.70	14.77
19.80	9.90
19.90	4.97
20.00	0.00
20.10	-5.02
20.20	-10.10
20.30	-15.23
20.40	-20.40
20.50	-25.62
20.60	-30.90

4 Exploring inertia with iterations

See a movie of what you will get...

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4a Exploring inertia with iterations

Creating the model...

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Particle Vector Pen Text Level Indicator Animation

Mathematical Model

$$x = \text{last}(x) + vx \times \Delta t$$
$$y = \text{last}(y) + vy \times \Delta t$$
$$vx = \text{last}(vx) + ax \times \Delta t$$
$$vy = \text{last}(vy) + ay \times \Delta t$$
$$ax = \frac{\text{sumFx}}{m}$$
$$ay = \frac{\text{sumFy}}{m}$$

4b Exploring inertia with iterations

Setting the scene... but there is a problem with the scale for the vector sum of the forces!

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The screenshot shows a software interface for a physics simulation. At the top, there are tabs for Home, Independent Variable, Model, Parameters, Initial Conditions, Table, Graph, Objects, Notes, and Animate. Below these are various control panels for a vector object named 'Vector1', including color (Red), coordinates (sumFx, sumFy), and scale (0.10). A 'Mathematical Model' panel contains the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned}
 x &= \text{last}(x) + vx \times \Delta t \\
 y &= \text{last}(y) + vy \times \Delta t \\
 vx &= \text{last}(vx) + ax \times \Delta t \\
 vy &= \text{last}(vy) + ay \times \Delta t \\
 ax &= \frac{\text{sumFx}}{m} \\
 ay &= \frac{\text{sumFy}}{m}
 \end{aligned}$$

The 'Graph' panel shows a plot of position versus time with a curve and a point labeled 'x = 54.14'. The 'Table' panel displays a data table with columns for time (t) and position (x):

t	x
4.00	209.4
4.90	207.4
5.00	203.5
5.10	199.5
5.20	193.4
5.30	186.4
5.40	178.2
5.50	168.8
5.60	158.1
5.70	146.2
5.80	133.1
5.90	119.0
6.00	103.9
6.10	87.7
6.20	71.2
6.30	54.1

At the bottom, there is a 'Notes' panel and a timeline with a play button and a slider set to t = 6.30. A small inset shows the force components: sumFy = 100.00 and sumFx = -40.00.

4C Exploring inertia with iterations

Changing the scale for the sumF vector makes it more easy to control velocity...

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5 Chemical equilibrium with differential equations

The model. The graph shows how the system reacts to change in the concentration of a reactant

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Mathematical Model

$$\frac{dA}{dt} = -v1 + v2$$
$$\frac{dB}{dt} = v1 - v2$$
$$v1 = k1 \times A$$
$$v2 = k2 \times B$$

Graph

The graph plots concentration (y-axis, -0.50 to 3.00) against time (x-axis, 0.00 to 32.00). A red curve represents concentration A, which starts at 2.00, drops to a minimum of approximately 0.50 at t = 8.00, and then rises to a new equilibrium value of 0.88. A blue curve represents concentration B, which starts at 0.00, rises to a peak of approximately 1.50 at t = 8.00, and then settles at a new equilibrium value of 2.33. A vertical dashed line is drawn at t = 28.30, indicating the time of the perturbation.

Table

t	A
26.80	0.87
26.90	0.87
27.00	0.87
27.10	0.87
27.20	0.87
27.30	0.87
27.40	0.87
27.50	0.87
27.60	0.87
27.70	0.87
27.80	0.87
27.90	0.87
28.00	0.87
28.10	0.87
28.20	0.87
28.30	0.88

Visual Model

The visual model shows two connected tanks. The left tank (blue) has a volume of 2.00 and a concentration of A = 0.88. The right tank (red) has a volume of 2.33 and a concentration of B = 2.33. Sliders for the rate constants are shown below: k1 = 0.64 and k2 = 0.24.

5a Chemical equilibrium with differential equations

Creating the model...

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The screenshot shows the Modellus software interface. The title bar reads "Modellus - New Document". The menu bar includes "Home", "Independent Variable", "Model", "Parameters", "Initial Conditions", and "Ta". The "Model" menu is active, displaying a toolbar with icons for "Copy Image", "Interpret", "Power" (x^n), "Square Root" (\sqrt{x}), "PI" (π), "e", and "Delta" (Δ). Below the toolbar is a "Mathematical Model" window containing the following equations:

$$\frac{dA}{dt} = -v1 + v2$$
$$\frac{dB}{dt} = v1 - v2$$
$$v1 = k1 \times A$$
$$v2 = k2 \times B$$

A yellow circle highlights a mouse cursor pointing at the bottom right corner of the "Mathematical Model" window.

5b Chemical equilibrium with differential equations

Creating controls for initial values and for parameters... and giving values for them

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Independent Variable Model Parameters Initial Conditions Table Graph Objects Notes

Pen Text Level Indicator Analog Variable Image Geometric Object Origin Measure Coordinates Measure Distance Copy Image Clipboard

Animation Objects

Model

Graph

t	A
0.00	1

A = 1.15

B = 0.42

k1 = 0.46

k2 = 0.73

5C Chemical equilibrium with differential equations

Running the model and changing values interactively...

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Modellus 4, A Visual Introduction for Teachers

The screenshot shows the Modellus software interface with the following components:

- Mathematical Model:**
$$\frac{dA}{dt} = -v1 + v2$$
$$\frac{dB}{dt} = v1 - v2$$
$$v1 = k1 \times A$$
$$v2 = k2 \times B$$
- Graph:** A plot showing the variables A (blue), B (red), and v2 (black) over time. The x-axis represents time (t) from 0.00 to 48.00, and the y-axis represents the variable values from 0.00 to 1.50. The graph shows step-like changes in the variables.
- Table:** A data table with columns for time (t) and variable A. The data points are as follows:

t	A
48.50	0.79
48.60	0.79
48.70	0.79
48.80	0.79
48.90	0.79
49.00	0.79
49.10	0.79
49.20	0.79
49.30	0.79
49.40	0.79
49.50	0.79
49.60	0.79
49.70	0.79
49.80	0.79
49.90	0.79
50.00	0.79
- Visual Model:** Four diagrams of a two-chamber system. The top-left chamber has A = 0.7 and B = 0.0. The top-right chamber has A = 0.51 and B = 0.0. The bottom-left chamber has A = 0.46 and B = 0.0. The bottom-right chamber has A = 0.72 and B = 0.0.
- Notes:** A text area at the bottom left.
- Timeline:** A slider at the bottom right showing the current time t = 50.00, with a range from Min: 0.00 to Max: 50.00.